

COMPOSITION OF MERCURY FERRO- AND FERRICYANIDES BY
PHYSICO-CHEMICAL METHODS. PART I. STUDY OF THE
COMPOSITION OF MERCURIC FERROCYANIDE
COMPLEX BY CONDUCTOMETRIC METHOD

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The composition of mercury ferrocyanide has been studied by conductometric titrations of mercuric nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide solutions employing different concentrations of the reactants in aqueous and aqueous alcoholic solutions. Many interesting complexes of additive nature are shown to be formed by the conductivity curves. Formation of such compounds in the direct and reverse titrations has been explained.

The behaviour of mercury salts has been found to be much more complicated than that of other heavy metals. Many complex formations of soluble and insoluble type have been reported when some mercury compounds are reacted by other neutral salts. It is well known that when mercuric chloride or mercuric nitrate is acted upon by potassium ferrocyanide, a greenish precipitate of mercuric ferrocyanide is obtained.

Reference in the literature about the elaborate study of the composition of mercuric ferrocyanide is scarcely available. Williamson ("Chemistry of Cyanogen Compounds", p. 125) states that a white precipitate of mercuric ferrocyanide is at first formed by adding mercuric chloride to a ferrocyanide solution. The precipitate gradually decomposes on keeping and finally turns blue. According to Schroder (Meilor, "Treatise on Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. IV, p. 831; a yellow precipitate of mercuric ferrocyanide is formed with concentrated solutions of potassium ferrocyanide and mercuric chloride. Bombelli (*Anal. Asoc. Quim. Argentina*, 1937, 27, 172) observed only that Hg_2FeCy_6 was decomposed by water. It was therefore considered worthy of interest to apply physico-chemical methods to elucidate the composition of the complex in the precipitated state. Conductivity titrations have been performed and they reveal many interesting facts regarding the behaviour and nature of mercuric ferrocyanide. Mercuric chloride was first of all titrated with potassium ferrocyanide but no tangible points of intersection in the conductivity curves were observed, when potassium ferrocyanide was added to mercuric chloride in the cell. Since mercuric chloride is very feebly dissociated, mercuric nitrate was taken as one of the reactants and conductivity titrations against potassium ferrocyanide were performed by dissolving the former in a minimum quantity of dilute nitric acid. Under these conditions the conductometric titrations could be followed and the formation of several complexes was indicated by the titration curves.

EXPERIMENTAL

AnalaR (B.D.H.) reagents were used. Preparation of standard solutions and further dilutions were done with conductivity water. Potassium ferrocyanide solution was estimated by titrating against standardised potassium permanganate solution

(Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", Part II, p. 536). Mercuric nitrate forms basic salts in water (Mellor, *loc. cit.*, p. 994) and so the solution was prepared in the least quantity of dilute nitric acid. The solution of mercuric nitrate was estimated by precipitating as sulphide (cf. Treadwell and Hall, *loc. cit.*, p. 172). The measurements of conductivity were done by Kohlrausch's Universal Bridge (W.G.Pye). As a source of A.C., a low frequency oscillator (1000 c/s Philips type 4260/1, No. RT-167) was used, the point of balance being indicated by a minimum of sound in the headphone. The conductivity cell was of Arrhenius type and during the course of titrations it was kept immersed in a thermostat maintained at room temperature (29°). The titrations were carried out by taking 10 c.c. of one of the reactants in the conductivity cell while the other was added gradually from the burette. The conductance of the solution after each addition was measured and was corrected for dilution effect by multiplying the observed conductance by $V/10$, where V was the total volume of the solution and 10 c.c. referred to the volume of the reactant taken in the cell (Davies, "The Conductivity of Solutions", p. 238). Curves were plotted between the corrected conductance thus obtained against the volume of the titrant. The breaks in the curves correspond to the formation of the different compounds. Using different concentrations of the two salt solutions, titrations were performed by direct and reverse methods, *i.e.*, when mercuric nitrate from the burette was added to potassium ferrocyanide in the cell and *vice versa*. Titrations were also done in the presence of alcohol up to 20 % by volume in the case of direct and 2 % by volume in the case of reverse titrations.

From the direct titration curves it follows that the formation of various complexes of mercuric ferrocyanide does not show any constancy of the number and the nature of compounds when the concentrations of the reactants are varied.

When direct titrations are carried out in presence of alcohol added to potassium ferrocyanide in the titration cell, it is remarkable that the breaks in the titration curves are fewer. The compositions of the variety of compounds formed at the respective breaks, though similar, are not identical with those obtained in the aqueous solution (Figs. 2-3).

In reverse titrations the formation of compounds is different from those of the direct titrations. Nature of the compounds shown by the reverse titration curves are similar but not identical (Figs. 4, 5 and 6).

In the reverse titrations alcohol added was only up to 2% in view of the low ionisation of mercuric nitrate. Addition of alcohol changes the composition of the complexes as potassium ferrocyanide is gradually added to mercuric nitrate (Figs. 5 and 6).

It will be evident from the titration curves that the compounds Hg_2FeCy_6 is positively formed both in the direct and reverse titrations and at all concentration ratios of the reactants. Other compounds are of the type of additive compounds consisting of a mercury ferrocyanide complex and mercuric nitrate or potassium ferrocyanide according to the ratio of concentrations of the reactants and also the order of mixing them (direct or reverse).

Fig. 2

10% Alcohol in K_4FeC_6 soln.

$M/5-Hg(NO_3)_2$ added in c.c.

$M/5-Hg(NO_3)_2$ and $M/5-K_4FeC_6$

Fig. 1

Aqueous.

$M/5-Hg(NO_3)_2$ added in c.c.

$M/5-Hg(NO_3)_2$ and $M/25-K_4FeC_6$

Fig. 4
Aqueous.

M/10- K_4FeCy_6 added in c.c.
M/10- K_4FeCy_6 and M/25- $Hg(NO_3)_2$.

Fig. 3
20% Alcohol in K_4FeCy_6 soln

M/5- $Hg(NO_3)_2$ added in c.c.
M/5- $Hg(NO_3)_2$ and M/25- K_4FeCy_6 .

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Both in the direct and reverse titrations the common complexes formed appear to be of the following compositions :

1. Hg_2FeCy_6
2. $\text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6, x\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$
3. $\text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6, x\text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6$

There is also an indication of the formation of a special type such as $\text{Hg}_2\text{FeCy}_6, x\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ by direct titration and of the type (i) $\text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6, \text{Hg}_2\text{FeCy}_6, x\text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6$ and (ii) $\text{Hg}_2\text{FeCy}_6, x\text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6$, in the reverse titrations.

All the above observations made from the characteristic conductivity-titration curves clearly suggest that the number and nature of mercuric ferrocyanide complexes remarkably vary in their composition both in aqueous and aq.-alcoholic solutions with the changes in the concentration ratio of the reactants. It may further be mentioned that when mercuric nitrate is added dropwise to an excess of potassium ferrocyanide, a yellowish precipitate is first formed which quickly dissolves just only up to a few drops (3 or 4) after which a yellow precipitate reappears which changes to permanent greenish precipitate on adding more and more of mercuric nitrate. It may be a soluble complex formed just at the beginning of which no indication is given by the conductivity curves.

DISCUSSION

The conductivity curves show the formation of different additive complexes between mercuric nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide under different concentration ratios of the reactants. In the direct titrations (Figs. 1-3) the mechanism of the reaction may be visualised by the following scheme :

- (a) $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + \text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6 = \text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6 + 2\text{KNO}_3$
- (b) $\text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6 + x\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 = \text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6, x\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ where $x < \text{one equivalent}$.
- (c) $\text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6 + \text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 = \text{Hg}_2\text{FeCy}_6 + 2\text{KNO}_3$
- (d) $\text{Hg}_2\text{FeCy}_6 + x\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 = \text{Hg}_2\text{FeCy}_6, x\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$

The compounds indicated by the conductivity titration curves seem to support the above mechanism.

In the case of reverse titrations the mechanism of the reaction can be visualised as under :

- (a) $2\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + \text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6 = \text{Hg}_2\text{FeCy}_6 + 4\text{KNO}_3$
- (b) $\text{Hg}_2\text{FeCy}_6 + x\text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6 = \text{Hg}_2\text{FeCy}_6, x\text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6$ where $x < \text{one equivalent}$.
- (c) $\text{Hg}_2\text{FeCy}_6 + \text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6 = 2\text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6$
- (d) $\text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6 + x\text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6 = \text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6, x\text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6$

At certain stage of the reaction there is also a possibility of a special case of combination as :

- (a) $\text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6 + x\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 = \text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6, x\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$
- (b) $\text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6 + \text{Hg}_2\text{FeCy}_6 + x\text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6 = \text{K}_2\text{HgFeCy}_6, \text{Hg}_2\text{FeCy}_6, x\text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6$

as supported by curves.

The above mechanism explains the formation of all the compounds marked in the conductivity curves.

Considering the dense nature of the precipitate of mercuric ferrocyanide it is very probable that the phenomenon of adsorption of the reacting ions may play an important rôle in the formation of these additive complexes.

Experiments are in progress to ascertain quantitatively the adsorption capacity of mercuric ferrocyanide for mercuric and potassium ferrocyanide, which may throw further light on the composition of the complex.

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